

Organizational policy as a moderator between online social networking and job performance

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Citation:

Wickramasinghe, V., & Nisaf, M.S.M. (2013). Organizational policy as a moderator between online social networking and job performance. VINE: The Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems, 43 (2), 161-184.

This Version is available at: doi: 10.1108/03055721311329945

Organizational policy as a moderator between online social networking and job performance

Purpose- To investigate the moderating effect of organizational policy on the relationship between online social networking and job performance of IT professionals engaged full-time in offshore outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach- Survey methodology was used and a random sample of 215 respondents who fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study, responded. To examine the hypothesized relationships factor analysis and multiple regression were used.

Findings- It was found that individuals engaged in online social networking while at work enjoy several benefits such as solving work-related problems collaboratively. However, individuals also suffer from several drawbacks, which could be mainly categorized into two in terms of interference to job tasks and interference to workplace. Further, it was found that online social networking has significant effects on individual job performance; organizational policy moderates the relationship between online social networking and job performance.

Originality/value- Although online social networking has attracted a substantial amount of media attention over the last few years empirical research attempts have not taken off worldwide. Therefore, the influence of online social networking on employee job performance would be of interest to academics and practitioners worldwide. It is expected that the findings of this study will provide insight into benefits, challenges and issues associated with OSN to allow individuals, organizational leaders, and IT decision-makers to better understand and utilize online social structures for success. Further, it is expected that the findings of this study will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Keywords: job performance, online social networking, offshore IT firms, social networking sites, Sri Lanka.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

A social network can be identified as a social structure comprised of individuals or organizations that are connected by one or more specific types of relation such as group work, kinship, friendship, trading relations, and professional associations (Barnes, 1954). Individuals' need to connect with people to collaborate, participate and share experience and learning as well as to gain new knowledge has increasingly drawing them into the online world (Coyle and Vaughn, 2008; Department for Communities and Local Government, 2008). The term online social networking (OSN) or social networking sites (SNS) is used to refer to a full range of products and services across platforms, which include content creation, networking, sharing and collaboration and which support existing offline networks or the creation of new ones (Dawley, 2009; Dougherty and Fanelli, 2008; Lai and Turban, 2008). The literature indicates that OSN facilitates building individual relationships, expanding personal networks, finding people who have had similar experiences, discussing common topics of interest, dating and finding potential life partners, and staying connected to friends, distant family members and work colleagues (Ferreira and du Plessis, 2009). Therefore, previous studies suggest that by utilizing electronic media and Web 2.0 tools such as Wiki's, blogs, tagging and social book-marking, OSN performs important functions of determining the way individuals/groups operate, problems are solved, and the extent to which people succeed in attaining their goals (Johnson and Ambrose, 2006).

The literature suggests that OSN is very popular amongst office workers due to the availability of Internet access, working from home facility, and the increasing erosion of traditional concepts of office hours (Shirky, 2008; Tapscott and Williams, 2006). Further, Dessler (2005) states that organizations empower employees to increase their levels of effectiveness and such empowered employees need information for them to act upon. One of the primary sources of information for employees would be through Internet (Hu *et al.*, 2006). In this regard, Hu *et al.* (2006) suggest that it is very much likely that employees may use part of the infrastructure provided by organizations for their personal requirements and may access and join OSN. Therefore, OSN has also gained the reputation of negatively

effecting employee productivity and damaging organizations' reputation (MessageLabs, 2007).

Sri Lanka is experiencing an increase in the usage of OSN (Google Insight, n.d.). According to Google Insight (n.d.), *Facebook* along has had a significant growth in Sri Lanka during the period of 2007 to 2008 and it is expected to be growing at an accelerating phase over the years 2010 and 2011. However, according to Google Insight (n.d.), Sri Lanka has an Internet penetration rate of 5.5%. Considering the fact that the majority of Sri Lankans do not have personal computers/laptops at home, it is possible to assume that the majority access Internet from their workplaces. The current study was conducted in the context of offshore outsourced IT firms as these firms were identified by the authors to provide Internet access to their employees to accomplish job roles. In this regard, work styles adopted by IT firms can be identified as group based where employees have a high degree of flexibility in where they work and have a high degree of interaction with their work colleagues (Scott 2005; also refer to Haynes, 2007). Beyerlein *et al.* (1995) state that unpredictable, multidisciplinary, and non-repetitive nature of job tasks of knowledge workers require them to routinely collaborate with others to utilize multiple viewpoints in solving problems. Therefore, knowledge workers have to establish a network of connections inside as well as outside of the formal structure of the organization that are not necessarily prescribed by the organization to fulfil their job as well as their social needs (Scott, 2005).

Although OSN has attracted a substantial amount of media attention over the last few years, it has recently become the subject of academic inquiry (see Wills and Reeves, 2009). Further, Kotlarsky and Oshri (2005) state that the main focus of the information systems literature on globally distributed teams has been on technical aspects related to system development projects and behavioural aspects are often inadequately addressed. Furthermore, the review of literature suggests that the majority of research in the area of OSN has not been conducted as academic research (e.g. ClearSwift, 2007; Department for Communities and Local Government, 2008; Dougherty and Fanelli, 2008; Hu *et al.*, 2006); the majority of articles in academic publications are practitioner viewpoints (e.g. Borden *et*

al., 2008) or conceptual papers (e.g. Boyd and Ellison, 2007; Lai and Turban, 2008; Schneckenberg, 2009; van Zyl, 2009). Although a few empirical research studies have been conducted on OSN (e.g. Brandtzæg *et al.*, 2010; Ferreira and du Plessis, 2009; Hasgall and Shoham, 2007; Ji *et al.*, 2010; Kim *et al.*, 2010) such empirical research attempts have not taken off worldwide. Our review of literature has been unable to find empirical studies that investigated the influence of OSN on employee job performance.

In the above context, the study investigated the moderating effect of organizational policies on the relationship between OSN and job performance of IT professionals engaged full-time in offshore outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka (refer to Figure 1). Specifically, the study investigated 1) benefits that individuals experience (such as collaborative learning), 2) drawbacks that individuals' experience (such as introducing viruses, worms and spyware to the organization's ICT infrastructure), and 3) the moderating effect of organizational policy on the relationship between benefits and drawbacks of OSN and job performance (refer to Figure 1). It is expected that the findings of this study will provide insight into benefits, challenges and issues associated with OSN to allow individuals, organizational leaders, and IT decision-makers to better understand and utilize online social structures for success. Further, it is expected that the findings of this study will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area. In order to provide context for this article, in the next section, the relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

Online social networking

Borden *et al.* (2008, p. 2) after reviewing various sources on social networks, define a social network as “a social structure made of individuals who are connected by one or more affinities or similarities such as values, religion, friendship, or any other shared

characteristics". This concept of social networking is not new as human behaviour inherently promotes the formation of networks through social contact (Tapscott and Williams, 2007 p. 10). Today, due to the advancement in OSN technologies, it is possible to network much quicker and reach a much larger audience (Borden *et al.*, 2008; Boyd and Ellison, 2007; Ferreira and du Plessis, 2009).

Boyd and Ellison (2007) define OSN as "web-based services that allow individuals to (1) construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system. The nature and nomenclature of these connections may vary from site to site" (online). According to the Department for Communities and Local Government (2008, p. 9) capabilities of OSN have increased significantly by allowing third parties to develop their own applications for use on these sites. Further, the increasing ability to access these sites anytime and anywhere using different and affordable devices (such as mobile phones) offers the potential for even wider use (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2008).

Borden *et al.* (2008) identify common OSN tools as blogs, shared calendars, document management/shared workspace, discussion groups, social bookmarking, instant messaging, chat rooms, and Wikis. Of these OSN tools, blogs, shared calendars, discussion groups, and social bookmarking can be used to transfer knowledge within a community; instant messaging and chat rooms can be used to improve communication between individual community members; shared workspace can be used to encourage collaboration and track which community members have reviewed, revised, and approved key documents; and Wikis can be used to tap into collective knowledge (Borden *et al.*, 2008). Overall, OSN produce large quantities of personal information that is hosted in virtual environments for discovery by other people (Scale, 2008).

Effects of online social networking for work

Our review of literature suggests that the effects of OSN for work have been approached from two different angles, namely benefits and drawbacks that individuals' experience while at work. In the following paragraphs the literature was reviewed under these two broad perspectives, and thereby hypotheses were developed for benefits that individuals' experience while at work and for drawbacks that individuals' experience while at work, separately. Further, four hypotheses (two for benefits and two for drawbacks) were developed as per the guidelines proposed by Fraizer *et al.* (2004) to test the moderation using hierarchical regression analysis (refer to the section on *data analysis procedure*).

Benefits of online social networking for work. The literature reveals several benefits that individuals can have from OSN. For instance, Chu and Chan (2009) suggest that in today's rapidly changing business environment innovative organizations could use online communities to identify and capture new ideas for creating new products and services. Hence, as suggested by Chu and Chan (2009) individuals engaged in innovative firms, such as software development could use OSN to tap creativity, ingenuity, and knowledge concerning specific product domains from others such as customers, vendors, partners, suppliers and analysts. Further, the majority of studies suggest that increased collaboration through OSN stimulates knowledge sharing between individuals. OSN can create a collaborative learning environment within the social system of a workplace, where problems encountered are collectively solved and solutions are shared among peers (Boshoff and du Plessis, 2008; Davenport, 2001; Orlikowski, 2002). In this regard, Minocha (2009) suggests that people learn by looking at the contributions of others in collaborative working spaces such as Wiki and blogs, by seeing different approaches that others take, and by reflecting on their own contributions. In the context of knowledge workers, several previous studies suggest that OSN allows knowledge workers to aggregate information in an efficient manner by facilitating them to add labels (through links, tags and social bookmarks) to make material more persistent for easy retrieval and sharing (Borden *et al.*, 2008; Brandtzæg *et al.*, 2010; IBM, 2007).

Further, some previous studies suggest that OSN empowers individuals in the workplace (Hasgall and Shoham, 2007; Schneckenberg, 2009). For instance, Hasgall and Shoham (2007, p. 183) suggest that “network systems are based on real-time technology and enable quick and immediate update of activity at a level that is virtually trivial. It was actually these trivial activities that enhanced the level of trust, openness and empowerment of employees”.

Furthermore, previous studies suggest that OSN contributes to maintain morale and increase job satisfaction of employees (e.g. IBM, 2007; Smith and Kollock, 1999; van Zyl, 2009). In this regard, OSN rewards individuals’ contributions through ratings and the creation of followers, who link to or subscribe to a particular individual’s work (IBM, 2007; Smith and Kollock, 1999). Such digital reputations recognize an individual’s contributions to and beyond the immediate group and place a value on the individual’s knowledge and knowledge creation abilities as well as satisfy the individual’s desire for prestige and recognition (e.g. IBM, 2007; Smith and Kollock, 1999).

In addition, some studies (e.g. Minocha, 2009) suggest that OSN assists individuals to gain transferable skills that are useful for current and future work environments. According to Minocha (2009, p. 387), individuals can develop team-working skills and online collaboration and communication skills that will help them to fit easily into work settings.

Overall, the literature suggest that OSN will provide benefits such as improved collaboration and information sharing (e.g. Beyerlein *et al.*, 1995; Tapscott and Williams, 2006), enhanced communication among co-workers, business partners and customers (e.g. Minocha, 2009), and increased individual productivity (e.g. Ferreira and du Plessis, 2009). Therefore, based on the literature reviewed above and the results of factor analysis (refer to the section on *measures* and Table 2), it is proposed for the study:

Hypothesis 1: “Assistance to work” that individuals experience from OSN will be positively related to job performance.

The literature emphasises the need of dealing with Internet abuse and addiction at workplaces via organizational infrastructure (Chen et al., 2008; Ferreira and du Plessis, 2009; Welebir and Kleiner, 2005). To overcome such issues concerning employees' Internet use and to establish appropriate use while at work organizations introduce policies on Internet use and deploy defence technologies (Chen *et al.*, 2008; Ferreira and du Plessis, 2009; Welebir and Kleiner, 2005). Internet use policy can be identified as a written agreement for employees to comply with the rule of not engaging in Internet abuse activities (Young and Case, 2004). Therefore, organizations use this policy as an external containment or deterrent to combat with Internet use in the workplace. However, according to Chen *et al.* (2008) many users are addicted to Internet and have little control of not using it in the workplace. As reviewed above, OSN sites can create a collaborative learning environment and can assist in solving job related problems (refer to Boshoff and du Plessis, 2008; Davenport, 2001; Orlikowski, 2002). Therefore, it could be assumed that if an organization does not limit employees engaging in OSN, they will get more assistance from OSN sites for job performance. In this regard, during the preliminary investigations made by the authors to get an insight into the situation prevailing in Sri Lanka, it was revealed that many IT organizations do not have a policy on OSN usage or they are lenient on employees engaging in OSN while at work. Based on the literature reviewed above and the insight gained from the preliminary investigation conducted in Sri Lanka, for this study we propose that the existence of organizational policy on OSN usage will moderate the relationship between assistance that employees gain from OSN for work and job performance. Therefore, it is proposed for the study:

Hypothesis 2: Organizational policy will moderate the positive relationship between “Assistance to work” and job performance in such a way that job performance will be strengthened for a higher level of lenient organizational policy on employees engaging in OSN.

Drawbacks of online social networking for work. The literature provides evidence that some individuals may engage in OSN during work hours for work-related purposes while some others may be engaged in the same for personal use (Ariyur, 2008; Chen *et al.*, 2008; ClearSwift, 2007; Ferreira and du Plessis, 2009; MessageLabs, 2007; Shirky 2008). Therefore, the literature suggests the need of understanding negative effects of OSN for individuals and their workplaces (Ferreira and du Plessis, 2009; van Zyl, 2009).

Ashmore and Herman (2006) and Chen *et al.* (2008) suggest that the deviant use of Internet technology may distract employees from job tasks on hand and may engage in unproductive or unethical activities such as online shopping, news, music, chatting, auctioning, and games while at work. In this regard, Chen *et al.* (2008) and Stanton (2002) provide evidence that Internet addiction significantly impacts employees' Internet abuse at the workplace. For instance, employees' OSN addiction may result in a decline in employees productivity (Ferreira and du Plessis, 2009; Lichtash, 2004; van Zyl, 2009); they may rely on information from non-subject matter experts to complete job tasks suggesting a deviation for data collection from recommended sources (Ariyur, 2008; ClearSwift, 2007); they may propagate unsolicited messages; they may expose members to malware thereby introducing viruses, worms and spyware to the organization's ICT infrastructure (The European Network and Information Security Agency, 2007; Perkins, 2008); they may share pictures, music, videos, and other large files resulting in high bandwidth and storage consumption (Ashmore and Herman, 2006; Chen *et al.*, 2008; Lichtash, 2004); and organizations may find difficulties in maintaining discipline at work (van Zyl, 2009).

Therefore, scholars suggest that little or no control of Internet abuse, on the one hand, can entail an unproductive and uncompetitive work organization with substantial number of work hours are wasted and network resources are inefficiently used (Chen *et al.*, 2008). On the other hand, an intensive exposure to OSN can induce anxiety, intolerance, insomnia, depression, back aches, conflict and other disordered behaviours (Chen *et al.*, 2008). Further, Chen *et al.* (2008) suggest that Internet addicts usually have troubles socializing in the workplace when they are not with the computer. Furthermore, Lai and

Turban (2008) reports that in some organizations employees object to the use of collaboration and communication tools claiming that there is more work for them. Based on the literature reviewed above and the results of factor analysis (refer to the section on *measures* and Table 3), it is proposed for the study:

Hypothesis 3: “Interference to job tasks” that individuals experience from OSN will be negatively related to job performance.

Hypothesis 4: “Interference to workplace” that individuals experience from OSN will be negatively related to job performance.

Based on the literature reviewed earlier (such as Chen *et al.*, 2008; ClearSwift, 2007; Ferreira and du Plessis, 2009; Welebir and Kleiner, 2005) and the insight gained from the preliminary investigation conducted in Sri Lanka, for this study we propose that the existence of organizational policy will moderate the relationship between drawbacks of OSN for work (i.e., Interference to job tasks and Interference to workplace) and job performance.

Therefore, it is proposed for the study:

Hypothesis 5: Organizational policy will moderate the negative relationship between “Interference to job tasks” and job performance in such a way that job performance will be reduced for a higher level of lenient organizational policy on employees engaging in OSN.

Hypothesis 6: Organizational policy will moderate the negative relationship between “Interference to workplace” and job performance in such a way that job performance will be reduced for a higher level of lenient organizational policy on employees engaging in OSN

Figure 1 shows the hypothesised research model. As detailed in the section on *measures*, specific benefits and drawbacks were derived from the factor analysis.

Take in Figure 1

Methodology

Sample

A random sample of IT employees was selected from offshore outsourced IT firms. The following sample selection criteria were set for the study: 1) a firm should provide unlimited Internet access to its employees, 2) a firm should provide unrestricted Internet access to its employees, 3) a respondent's job tasks should require interaction with others, and 4) a respondent should have at least 6 months experience in using OSN. In the fourth quarter of 2010 authors identified 10 offshore IT firms that fulfil the first and second selection criteria set for the study. A contact person was identified at each firm. This person was asked to randomly select IT professionals who fulfil the third and fourth section criteria set for the study and to distribute the link to the online survey questionnaire via e-mail (also refer to the section on methods of data collection). Of the 300 self-administered questionnaires distributed in the fourth quarter of 2010, a total of 215 usable responses resulted in 72% response rate. The demographics of the sample are shown in Table 1. The age categorization of respondents reveal that mean age is 29 years. The frequency analysis revealed that the minimum age of the respondents is 25 years while the maximum age is 33 years. Hence, we have not made any divisions based on the age of the respondents in analyzing data. In this regard, industry statistics and previous studies (such as Wickramasinghe, 2009; World Bank, 2006) confirm that employees attached to offshore outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka belong to the age group of 25 to 35 years; this may be due to the nature of the Sri Lankan offshore outsourced IT sector, which is young.

Take in Table 1

Measures

The main constructs used in the study were benefits of OSN for work, drawbacks of OSN for work, individual job performance, and organizational policy on OSN usage at work. All the item measures were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree. For all measurement scales, standardised Cronbach's alpha was examined and Principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair *et al.*, 2006). The items were averaged to produce a mean score for the construct.

The benefits of OSN for work were measured by the seven-item scale developed based on the studies of Shirky (2008), Matuszak (2007), Boshoff and du Plessis (2008), and IBM (2007). Factor analysis yielded one factor, which explained 65% (65.37) of the variance. This factor was labelled as "Assistance to work". The standardised estimates and reliability statistics for this factor are provided in Table 2.

Take in Table 2

The drawbacks of OSN for work were measured by the eight-item scale developed based on the studies of Ferreira and du Plessis (2009), Ariyur (2008), MessageLabs (2007), ClearSwift (2007), Benkler (2006), and Graham and Hall (2004). The items had a reliability of 0.813. Factor analysis yielded a set of two factors, which explained 64% (63.61) of the variance. Of these two factors, Factor 1 was labelled as "Interference to job tasks" and Factor 2 as "Interference to workplace". The standardised estimates and reliability statistics for these factors are provided in Table 3.

Take in Table 3

Individual job performance was measured by the seven-item scale developed based on the studies of Department for Communities and Local Government (2008), Dessler (2005), and Haynes (2007). Factor analysis yielded one factor, which explained 61% (61.07) of the variance. The standardised estimates and reliability statistics for this factor are provided in Table 4.

Take in Table 4

Organizational policy on OSN was measured by a single item, i.e., “My organization has a lenient policy (with less restriction) on employees engaging in OSN”. This item measure was on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree (refer to Table 5).

Other than the above mentioned four main constructs, purposes for which respondents use OSN is also inquired in the study. The purposes of OSN were measured by the six-items developed based on the studies of Boyd and Ellison (2007), Lichtash (2004), and Ferreira and du Plessis (2009) (refer to Table 6). In addition, respondents’ years of OSN experience, the level of daily OSN usage, and the types of OSN sites used were also inquired in the study (refer to Table 5).

Seven individual demographic characteristics were controlled in the study. Age, work experience at the present workplace, total work experience, and the years of OSN experience were measured in years. Daily OSN usage was measured in hours. Gender (females = 0, males = 1) and marital status (single = 0, married = 1) were binary coded.

Methods of data collection

Considering the literacy of the respondents and amenability of the research questions, the self-administered survey questionnaire was in the English language. Considering the target audience of the study and their capabilities, an online questionnaire was developed. All the measures are self-report in nature. The questionnaire was pre-tested with a random sample of 20 employees engaged full-time in offshore outsourced IT firms. The response rate to the pre-test is 100%. The analysis of pre-test data for item non-response rates and response distributions did not reveal any major issues with the survey questionnaire. The link to the pre-tested online survey was distributed among the random sample of employees (also refer to the section on sample) via e-mail.

Firms were reluctant to provide actual data on job performance. Hence, the study relied on self-assessed job performance. In this regard, Oseland (1999, p. 4) states that self-assessed performance is not a new measure, and suggests that perceived performance could be used as a surrogate for actual performance. Further, Oseland (1999) suggests that research with a larger sample instills confidence in the self-assessment measure. Yet, when self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature highlights the problem of common method bias (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003; Spector 1994). Therefore, procedural and statistical measures were taken to reduce common method bias in the current study. First, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension (a procedure recommended by Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). Second, factor analysis was used to conduct Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff *et al.* (2003).

Data analysis procedure

Hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to test the moderation effect. The literature recommends that when the predictor and moderator variables are measured on a

continuous scale, the hierarchical regression procedure that retains the continuous nature of the variables is preferred over using cut points (Aiken and West, 1991). Therefore, hierarchical regression was used to test the hypothesised relationships (also refer to Fraizer et al., 2004). The variables were mean centred to increase interpretability of interactions (see Fraizer *et al.*, 2004). The variables were entered into the regression equation in four steps. The control variables were entered in the first step, the independent variable was added in the second step, the moderator variable was added in the third step, and the interaction term was added in the fourth step (see Fraizer *et al.*, 2004). The plots were constructed by plotting low, medium and high scores of the variables. For this, Jose's (2002) Excel version of ModGraph programme for continuous variables was used. Following the recommendations of Aiken and West (1991), simple effects tests were conducted to determine whether the slopes differed significantly from zero.

Results and discussion

Nature of OSN

Table 5 shows workplace policies on OSN, respondents' years of OSN usage experience, the level of daily OSN usage, and the types of OSN sites used. With regard to organizational policy on OSN, as shown in Table 5, a mean value of 3.80 suggests that organizations have a lenient policy (with less restriction) on employees engaging in OSN. However, a mean value of 2.44 suggests that organizations do not encourage employees to engage in OSN.

The data shown in Table 5 suggest that 60% of the respondents use workplace Internet facilities to be engaged in OSN, 79% of the respondents has more than 2 years of experience with OSN, and they are engaged on average three and half hours of OSN per day. In this regard, Dawley (2009) suggests that credibility and expertise in social networking comes from the extent of involvement in the network including the amount of participation, frequency, and the usefulness of the information provided. Zhou (2011) also found that online community user participation is affected by social identity as users are members of a collective group and by group norms on shared goals and expectations. The most popular

OSN sites were Facebook, YouTube and Wikis. As suggested by Lee and Lee (2010), these online communities bring a variety of people together virtually from different backgrounds and allow them to find common ground in their beliefs and interests. As shown in Table 5, OSN sites are mostly used to socialize with others (e.g. Facebook), share videos (e.g. YouTube), and to tap into collective knowledge (e.g. Wikis).

Take in Table 5

Purposes of OSN

Table 6 shows the purposes of OSN. The items had a reliability of 0.807. Factor analysis yielded a set of two factors, which explained 72% (72.20) of the variance. Of these two factors, Factor 1 was labelled as “Work-related and professional purposes” and Factor 2 as “Non-work purposes”. Work-related and professional purposes included purposes such as to communicate with office colleagues, to find solutions to job quarries and to be connected with professional community. Non-work purposes included purposes such as to share content with friends and family and to strengthen social ties.

Take in Table 6

Benefits of OSN for work

As shown in Table 2, individuals engaged in OSN enjoy several benefits such as solving work-related problems collaboratively, obtaining help from colleagues to accomplish job tasks, and gaining knowledge from others. These findings support the findings of previous studies that claimed collaborative learning (e.g. Moller, 1998) and reflective practice (e.g. McNamara and Brown, 2009) are essential aspects of workplace learning. For instance, Moller (1998) states that collaborative learning processes promote the kind of learning

necessary for present and future work preparation. McNamara and Brown (2009) provide evidence that online discussions promote collaborative learning and reflective practice in the workplace. Further, Borden *et al.* (2008) provide evidence that OSN foster collaboration and information sharing between individuals who may be scattered across the country or even the globe.

Overall, the findings suggest that benefits individuals received from OSN are useful for the organizations. In other words, benefits gained from OSN by individuals for work suggest that OSN adds value to organizations. In this regard, Allee (2003) identifies such networks as value networks because of the tangible and intangible value flowing between groups of people. Mason *et al.* (2008) also state that such value networks are important because they increase the potential for innovation, improve the efficiency of systems, and provide access to accumulated entrepreneurial experience and specific knowledge. Mason *et al.* (2008) further state that the incorporation of ICT into value networks extends the reach so that individuals establish identity within a far wider network who do not know each other but share knowledge and combine their knowledge in new ways even though relationships are less intimate.

Drawbacks of OSN for work

As shown in Table 2, individuals suffer from several drawbacks and these could be mainly categorized into two, i.e., interference to job tasks and interference to workplace.

Interference to job tasks included drawbacks such as receiving information from OSN sites which cannot handle by individuals while at work, receiving information that are not useful for work and getting distracted from work. Interference to workplace included drawbacks such as office network tends to slow down when employees engaged in OSN and employees come across virus, spyware or spam attacks via OSN sites while at work. Prior studies by The European Network and Information Security Agency (2007), ClearSwift (2007) and MessageLabs (2007) also suggest that OSN expose members to malware thereby introducing viruses, worms and spyware to the organization's ICT infrastructure; OSN results

in bandwidth and storage consumption as many social network members share pictures, music, videos, and high-definition movies. In this regard, the literature on Internet abuse suggest that employees' misuse of Internet technologies in the workplace for non-work purposes can victimize an organization with overpaid wages, legal liabilities, lawsuits and the loss of goodwill (Stewart 2000). As suggested by von Mutius (2005) a little control on OSN can, ultimately, entail an unproductive and uncompetitive organization.

Influence of OSN on job performance

The main objective of the study was to investigate the moderating effect of organizational policy on the relationship between benefits (i.e., assistance to work) and drawbacks (i.e., interference to job tasks and interference to workplace) of OSN and individual job performance. For this, correlation and regression analyses were used as detailed in the section on *data analysis procedure*.

Descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations between the variables are shown in Table 7. The correlation between “assistance to work” and individual job performance is positive and significant. The correlation between “interference to job tasks” and job performance is negative and significant. The correlation between “interference to workplace” and job performance is also negative and significant.

Take in Table 7

Three separate hierarchical regression analyses were conducted to test the moderator effect of organizational policy. The results are shown in Tables 8, 9 and 10.

First, the effect of organizational policy as a moderator in assistance to work and job performance relationship was tested. The results are shown in Table 8. As shown in Table 8 (Model 2), assistance to work is significantly positively related to job performance ($p < .001$). This supports H1. As shown in Table 8 (Model 3), organizational policy significantly impacts

on job performance ($p < .01$). As indicated by the significant interaction term in Table 8 (Model 4), organizational policy moderates the relationship between assistance to work and job performance. The plot that illustrates the moderation is shown in Figure 2. The results of simple effects test revealed that the relationship between assistance to work and job performance is moderated for high ($t = 4.528, p < .001$) and medium ($t = 2.701, p < .01$) levels of lenient organizational policy (with less restriction) on employees engaging in OSN. This supports H2.

Take in Table 8

Take in Figure 2

Second, the effect of organizational policy as a moderator in interference to job tasks and job performance relationship was tested. The results are shown in Table 9. As shown in Table 9 (Model 2), interference to job tasks is significantly negatively related to job performance ($p < .001$). This supports H3. As shown in Table 9 (Model 3), organizational policy significantly impacts on job performance ($p < .01$). As indicated by the significant interaction term in Table 9 (Model 4), organizational policy moderates the relationship between interference to job tasks and job performance. The plot that illustrates the moderation is shown in Figure 3. The results of simple effects test revealed that the relationship between interference to job tasks and job performance is moderated for a high ($t = -1.970, p < .05$) level of lenient organizational policy (with less restriction) on employees engaging in OSN. This supports H5.

Take in Table 9

Take in Figure 3

Third, the effect of organizational policy as a moderator in interference to workplace and job performance relationship was tested. The results are shown in Table 10. As shown in Table 10 (Model 2), interference to workplace is significantly negatively related to job performance ($p < .01$). This supports H4. As shown in Table 10 (Model 3), organizational policy significantly impacts on job performance ($p < .05$). As indicated by the significant interaction term in Table 10 (Model 4), organizational policy moderates the relationship between interference to workplace and job performance. The plot that illustrates the moderation is shown in Figure 4. The results of simple effects test revealed that the relationship between interference to workplace and job performance is moderated for a high ($t = -3.015, p < .05$) level of lenient organizational policy (with less restriction) on employees engaging in OSN. This supports H6.

Take in Table 10

Take in Figure 4

Conclusions and implications

The paper presented a study conducted to understand the influence of OSN on individual job performance. The sample was selected in such a way that sample firms have provided unlimited and unrestricted Internet access to employees, their job tasks require interaction with others, and all respondents had at least six months experience in engaging in OSN. The findings of the study have both theoretical and practical implications.

With regard to theoretical implications, first, both academics and practitioners need valid information to better understand the influence of OSN on individual job performance. This becomes important because the popularity of OSN is relatively recent, and employees engaging in OSN during office work hours are growing while scholarly research in this area

is presently lacking. In this context, academics and practitioners could employ the multidimensional constructs proposed in this study as a diagnostic tool to assess and analyse issues in connection with the usage of OSN across similar and different samples and could take necessary corrective actions to optimize the benefits of OSN while minimizing the negative effects.

Second, the literature suggests that OSN has an impact on social capital (Wellman, 2001). OSN supports the development of wider communication and interaction and thus creates more opportunities to develop social capital from connections between individuals (Pigg and Crank, 2004; Stern and Dillman, 2006). In this sense too OSN contributes to an organization's ability for innovation and value creation (von Mutius, 2005) and consequently to achieve competitive advantage. Overall, whilst it is recognised that today's capital has expanded its scope to include social relationships as well, the literature provides little empirical evidence on the effect of OSN on employees and their workplaces. Therefore, the current study makes a contribution in that direction.

Third, the findings suggested a conflicting role of organizational policy in moderating the effects of OSN (positive and negative). This finding on the one hand emphasise the need of OSN usage policy to increase acceptable use to fulfil job tasks and well as the need of monitoring and filtering employees OSN use to enhance job performance. Organizations should find an avenue to demarcate these two aspects. The sample of the study represented a growing sector of the economy of Sri Lanka. However, the similar nature of work is done in many other countries across the world (World Bank 2006). Therefore, information on workers' job performance is of interest to many countries worldwide. However, the lack of availability of previous empirical studies that addressed the main variables investigated in this study made difficulties in making comparisons. Hence, considerable future research is necessary to validate the links suggested in this study.

With regard to implications of the findings for practice, first, it was found that the assistance employees received from OSN significantly positively related to individual job performance. The two factors of drawbacks of OSN (namely, interference to job tasks and

interference to workplace) significantly negatively influence job performance. In this regard, OSN facilitates individuals to access diverse resources that help them to accomplish their job tasks through building social and human capital, which in turn positively influence their job performance. On the other hand, distractions individuals experience through OSN adversely influence their job performance.

Second, in the global outsourcing environment, where organizational structures take on flatter and more decentralised form, putting a premium on individuals' social networks becomes beneficial for the firms. Our findings suggest that OSN has significant positive benefits for individual job performance. Therefore, it is beneficial for firms with a long term-view to pay more attention to evolving online social relationships among individual actors involving internal as well as external community and facilitate them to maintain such relationships. In this regard, de Janasz and Forret (2008) and Department for Communities and Local Government (2008) argue that many individuals feel uncomfortable with, or unskilled in, networking. Hence, the role of firms in enhancing employees' networking capabilities becomes important. In doing so, firms could develop online communities that share knowledge. In this regard, Chu and Chan (2009) suggested that organizations could aim to attract users to join online communities, and promote both the idea of a common goal and enthusiastically interactive discussions in which new ideas can be shared. Further, Zhou (2011) suggested that organizations could use social processes such as identification and internalization to enhance social identity and group norms to enhance user participation in online communities. When considering the high turnover rate of IT professionals of the Sri Lankan offshore outsourced IT industry (Wickramasinghe, 2009), firms could establish online alumni networks of former IT professionals. Through such initiatives firms could harness innate human behaviour to better manage knowledge and in turn become more competitive.

Third, the findings suggest that the advent of OSN has made it possible that employees also get distracted from work activities when they engage in OSN while at work. Therefore, the findings of the study suggest the need of implementing formal policies and procedures to establish appropriate use of OSN while at work. In this regard, Welebir and

Kleiner (2005, p. 80) state that when such OSN usage policies and procedures are tailored to fit an organization's culture, ultimately, the organizational culture will have the strongest effect on employees' behaviour at work.

Fourth, it was found that organization policy moderates the positive relationship between assistance employees received from OSN and job performance. Specifically, the positive relationship between "assistance to work" and job performance is strengthened for a higher level of lenient organizational policy on employees engaging in OSN. In this regard, correlation between a lenient organizational policy and "assistance to work" is positive and significant. At the same time, it was found that organization policy moderates the negative relationship between "interference to job tasks" and job performance as well as the negative relationship between "interference to workplace" and job performance. In this regard, correlation between a lenient organizational policy and "interference to job tasks" and "interference to workplace" are positive and significant. Therefore, organizational policy moderates the negative relationship between "interference to job tasks" and job performance as well as the negative relationship between "interference to workplace" and job performance in such a way that job performance is reduced for a higher level of lenient organizational policy on employees engaging in OSN. The main concern regarding these findings is the contradictory role of organization policy on employees engaging in OSN between assistance and interference of OSN and job performance. These findings imply difficulties organizations face in balancing both effects of OSN (positive and negative) by introducing OSN usage policy at work.

Limitations of the study and areas for future research

The data were collected from a considerably large homogeneous sample of IT professionals attached to offshore IT firms in Sri Lanka. The study relied on self-reported data. However, as mentioned in the section on *methods of data collection* attempts were made to overcome problems that may occur due to common method variance. With regard to areas for future research, the validity of a measure cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-

sectional study. The validation of a measure requires the assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts. Hence, future research, in different samples and longitudinal studies, are necessary that compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews. Further, the current study was confined to investigate the influence of OSN for individuals' work. We have not investigated, for instance, how individuals use OSN to develop electronic portfolios for future employment as well as how OSN is used to find job openings and to secure new employment opportunities. Furthermore, Borden et al. (2008) suggest that OSN is not appropriate for all audiences while the Department for Communities and Local Government (2008) suggest that OSN is not only popular with the young and tech-aware of the society but also popular among many other demographic groups. However, we were unable to make any comparison based on the age of the respondents as majority of employees attached to offshore outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka are young. Hence, future research could enhance the understanding by selecting a sample from diverse age groups. In addition, we investigated the moderating effect of organization policy. Future studies could incorporate moderating effects of other variables (such as the extent to which job requires social interaction) or there could be mediators in the relationship between OSN and job performance. Future research could incorporate such variables.

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Figures

Figure 1: Hypothesised research model

Figure 2. Assistance to work - job performance relationship moderated by organizational policy

Figure 3. Interference to job tasks - job performance relationship moderated by organizational policy

Figure 4. Interference to workplace - job performance relationship moderated by organizational policy

Tables

Table 1. Sample demographics

Age (in years):	
Mean	28.93
Std. Deviation	3.77
Skewness	1.68
Kurtosis	5.81
Gender:	
Female	24%
Male	76%
Marital status:	
Single	55%
Married	45%
Years of experience in the present workplace:	
Mean	4.17
Std. Deviation	2.19
Skewness	.94
Kurtosis	1.22
Total years of work experience:	
Mean	5.42
Std. Deviation	2.66
Skewness	1.51
Kurtosis	1.37
The highest level of education:	
Diploma	3%
Bachelor's degree	74%
Postgraduate degree	23%

Table 2. Summarised results: factor analysis – benefits of OSN for work

	Assistance to work
I solve work-related problems collaboratively through OSN	.894
I contact colleagues through OSN when I need help for my job tasks	.878
I obtain work-related advice through OSN	.875
OSN facilitates me to manage my work	.845
OSN gives me flexibility to work from home	.802
I access knowledge relevant to my job tasks through OSN	.743
I gain knowledge on regulatory procedures relevant to my work through OSN	.576
Explained variation	65.371
Eigenvalue	4.576
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.908

Table 3. Summarised results: factor analysis – drawbacks of OSN for work

	F 1 Interference to job tasks	F 2 Interference to workplace
I get information through OSN which I cannot handle while at work	.839	
I get a number of help requests through OSN which I cannot handle while at work	.820	
Most of the information I get through OSN are not useful for my work	.781	
Mostly I get disturbed when I engaged in OSN while at work	.767	
OSN distracts me from my work	.692	
My office network tends to slow down when employees are engaged in OSN		.811
Employees came across virus, spyware or spam attacks via OSN while at work		.784
Explained variation	43.720	19.889
Eigenvalue	3.498	1.591
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.810	.779

Table 4. Summarised results: factor analysis – individual job performance

	Job performance
I utilize my working time to deliver a quality output	.774
I meet deadlines given to me	.724
I effectively manage my job tasks	.841
I solve problems faster	.856
My work is error free	.751
I deliver better output than my colleagues on time	.694
I achieve my pre-determined work standards	.816
Explained variation	61.073
Eigenvalue	4.275
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.892

Table 5. Nature of OSN

<i>Purposes for which Internet is mainly used at work:</i>	
Social networking	60%
Educational purposes	22%
To read news	18%
<i>Years of OSN experience:</i>	
Six months to 2 years	21%
More than 2 years	79%
<i>OSN usage per day (in hours):</i>	
Mean	3.52
Std. Deviation	2.06
Skewness	1.80
Kurtosis	2.29
<i>Types of OSN sites used:</i>	
Facebook	26%
YouTube	18%
Wikis	18%
LinkedIn	8%
Google docs	8%
Ebay	8%
Flickr	4%
Amazon	4%
Twitter	3%
Blogger	3%
<i>Encouragement from the organization to engage in OSN (Organization encourages employees to engage in OSN[†]):</i>	
Mean	2.44
Std. Deviation	0.97
<i>Organization policy on OSN (Organization has a lenient policy (with less restriction) on employees engaging in OSN[†]):</i>	
Mean	3.80
Std. Deviation	1.08

[†] Scale: 5 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree)

Table 6. Summarised results: factor analysis – purposes of OSN

	F 1 Work-related and professional purposes	F 2 Non-work purposes
I engage in OSN to find solutions for job quarries	.880	
I engage in OSN to communicate work with colleagues	.846	
I engage in OSN to communicate with professionals who live locally/internationally	.745	
I engage in OSN to share various content (such as photos and videos) with my friends		.870
I engage in OSN to socialize with friends		.804
I engage in OSN to communicate with my social contacts (such as friends and family) who live locally/internationally		.656
Explained variation	51.66	20.54
Eigenvalue	3.100	1.230
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.752	.811

Table 7. Correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1 Age	28.93	3.76	1										
2 Gender	.76	.42	.143*	1									
3 Marital status	.45	.49	.372**	.076	1								
4 Firm tenure	4.17	2.18	.646**	.013	.221**	1							
5 Total tenure	5.42	2.65	.780**	.083	.361**	.714**	1						
6 OSN experience	1.79	.41	.066	.129	-.028	.038	.057	1					
7 OSN usage	3.52	2.06	.075	.004	-.015	.171*	.127	.013	1				
8 Organization policy [†]	3.80	1.08	.022	.069	.011	.131	-.054	.116*	-.216*	1			
9 Assistance to work	3.18	.85	.004	.165*	-.131	.121	.022	.100	.113	.238**	1		
10 Interference to job tasks	2.88	.73	.017	.035	.043	.035	.057	.071	.092	.232**	.165*	1	
11 Interference to workplace	2.22	.77	.050	.116	.133	.061	.064	.082	.090	.225**	.173*	.104	1
12 Job performance	3.91	.61	.079	.094	.106	.104	.141*	.126	.056	.211**	.273**	-.233**	-.293**

Note: * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

[†] Lenient policy (with less restriction) on employees engaging in OSN (scale: 1= strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree)

Table 8. Results of hierarchical regression for assistance to work-organizational policy-job performance relationship

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>Step 1: Control</i>				
Age	.110	.087	.080	.066
Gender	.074	.050	.047	.053
Marital status	.089	.120	.102	.034
Firm tenure	.017	.020	.088	.147
Total tenure	.125	.178	.241*	.205*
OSN experience	.088	.107	.087	.106*
OSN usage	.036	.042	.046	.035
<i>Step 2: Independent</i>				
Assistance to work		.258***	.221***	.418***
<i>Step 3: Moderator</i>				
Organization OSN policy [†]			.203**	.233**
<i>Step 4: Interaction term</i>				
Assistance to work X Organizational policy				.563***
R ² (Adj.)	.031	.086	.119	.168
F change	1.981	3.513**	4.225***	5.361***
ΔR ²	.063	.120	.156	.208

Note: * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<.001

[†] Lenient policy (with less restriction) on employees engaging in OSN (scale: 1= strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree)

Table 9. Results of hierarchical regression for interference to job tasks-organizational policy-job performance relationship

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>Step 1: Control</i>				
Age	.110	.127	.113	.015
Gender	.074	.124	.110	.051
Marital status	.089	.072	.062	-.026
Firm tenure	.017	.032	.041	.076
Total tenure	.125	.216	.269*	.100*
OSN experience	.088	.123	.102	.092*
OSN usage	.036	.060	.062	
<i>Step 2: Independent</i>				
Interference to job tasks		-.236***	-.192***	-.375***
<i>Step 3: Moderator</i>				
Organization OSN policy [†]			.196**	.217**
<i>Step 4: Interaction term</i>				
Interference to job tasks X Organizational policy				-.400***
R ² (Adj.)	.031	.083	.113	.178
F change	1.981	3.411**	4.019***	5.628***
ΔR ²	.063	.117	.150	.216

Note: * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<.001

[†] Lenient policy (with less restriction) on employees engaging in OSN (scale: 1= strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree)

Table 10. Results of hierarchical regression for interference to workplace-organizational policy-job performance relationship

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>Step 1: Control</i>				
Age	.110	.103	.093	.097
Gender	.074	.105	.086	.087
Marital status	.089	.102	.089	.008
Firm tenure	.017	.034	.059	.050
Total tenure	.125*	.165*	.240*	.216*
OSN experience	.088	.146*	.117	.114
OSN usage	.036	.070	.067	.076
<i>Step 2: Independent</i>				
Interference to workplace		-.187**	-.203**	-.285**
<i>Step 3: Moderator</i>				
Organization OSN policy [†]			.153*	.198*
<i>Step 4: Interaction term</i>				
Interference to workplace X Organizational policy				.483***
R ² (Adj.)	.031	.034	.087	.256
F change	1.981	1.930	3.275**	8.359***
ΔR ²	.063	.070	.126	.291

Note: * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<.001

[†] Lenient policy (with less restriction) on employees engaging in OSN (scale: 1= strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree)